

ASSESSMENT OF AGGRESSION AND ANXIETY IN DIFFERENT LEVELS OF VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to assess the aggression and anxiety in different levels of volleyball players. For the purpose of the study, two groups namely higher and lower performance group were created. The higher performance group was composed of those players who had participated in senior state championship. Whereas lower performance group was composed of those players, who had participated in open district championship but could not be selected to represent the district team. Sports aggression inventory & competitive state anxiety inventory-2, Questionnaire tests were selected to collect the data. The C.S.A.I. questionnaires were administered to each player prior to the competition. Whereas sports aggression questionnaires were distributed to the athletes for their response immediately after the competition. To find the significance difference between high and low performance volleyball players on aggression and anxiety, the 't' ratio was applied. The level of significance was set at .05. The result revealed that the high performance volleyball players had significantly more aggressive attitude than those of low performance volleyball players. The result also revealed that there is no significant difference between high and low level performance ability volleyball players in the dimension of anxiety.

Keywords: aggression, anxiety, volleyball

1. Introduction

Proficiency in any sport and game requires the ideal combination and interaction of numerous abilities developed to an ideal degree. However, performance measures of this ability vary from activity to activity.

Anyone who has seen children participating in an exciting competitive game cannot doubt that emotions are being expressed and it has often been suggested that competitive sports represent a valuable means of sublimating aggressive impulses.

When aggressive energies are expressed within the rules of a sport and channeled into skill by a mature athlete, then one may witness a powerful and inspiring performance. The outstanding athlete's enter competition with control and not with impulse. The aggressive athletes will be more active, eager, strong, highly motivated and likely to seek to vanquish an opponent.

Anxiety is related to emotional stability, tough-mindedness and confidence, a person who possesses the above qualities is equipped to handle anxiety and convert it into something very productive.

Anxiety may be motivating force or it may interfere with successful athletic performance. As a positive motivating force, it can be instrumental in motivating the athlete to work harder to find new and better ways to improve performance and to help set goals. The athlete who uses his anxiety in this well seek out ways to improve himself, not only reduces anxiety but also help him to increase his athletic skills and his self-confidence.

2. Method

Sixty male volleyball players of different levels were selected as subjects for this study. Players who had participated in U.P. State volleyball Championship were formed higher performance group and those who had participated in open district championship but could not be selected to represent the District team formed the "low performance" group, each group consisted of 30 players and their age range from 17 to 25 years.

In order to find out the competitive sport Anxiety of Volleyball players C.S.A.I-2 form was applied. The Questionnaire consists of 27 statements which had an evaluation range from 1 = not at all to 4 = very much so. The Questionnaire assesses the following two components and third factor – (A). Cognitive Anxiety (B). Somatic Anxiety. (c) Self Confidence. In order to find the competition Anxiety of the subjects, the scores on the above mentioned factors were added up.

"Sports Aggression Inventory" constructed by Anand Kumar and Prem Shanker Shukla, was selected for this study. This inventory consists of 25 items in which 13 items are keyed "Yes" and rests of 12 items are keyed "No". The score obtained by each subjects, on each statement was added up which represented one's total score on Aggression.

In order to assess the significant difference between high performance and low performance volleyball players on Aggression and Competition Anxiety, the t-ratio was applied. The level of significance was set at .05.

3. Findings

To determine the significance of mean difference between low and high performance volleyball players with regard to their psychological dimensions Aggression and Anxiety status is presented in Table 1:

Table 1: Significance of Difference of Means of High And Low Performance Volleyball Players

S. No	Group	Dimensions	Mean	S.D.	Mean difference	Std. Error of the mean	t-ratio
1	High Perf	Aggression	12.5	4.25			
					2.57	0.945	2.71*
2	Low Perf	Aggression	9.93	2.95			
3	High Perf	Anxiety	62.0	5.69			
					2.60	1.09	1.36
4	Low Perf	Anxiety	64.6	8.75			

* Significant at 0.05 level of confidence.

't' value required to be significant at 0.05 level with 58 degree of freedom is 2.0

The analysis of data in table -1 shows that high performance volleyball players have significantly more Aggressive attitude than those of low performance volleyball players as the obtained 't' value of 2.71 is higher than the required value of 2.0.

The analysis of data also reveals that there is no significant difference between high and low level performance ability volleyball players in the dimension of Anxiety as the obtained 't' value of 1.36 is lower than the required 't' value of 2.0 at 0.05 level of confidence.

4. Discussions of Findings

The significant difference between high and low performance volleyball players in the dimension of Aggression may be due to the fact that the maturity of these experienced players might be helping them to produce optimum amount of Aggression when it is required and channelise it into skill which may lead to inspiring performance as the optimum level of Aggressiveness makes the player more active, eager and highly motivated.

Insignificant difference between the high and low performance volleyball players in the dimension of anxiety may be attributed to the fact that regular participation in game of volleyball by both category of players might have produced in them the quality of emotional stability, tough-mindedness and self-confidence and these qualities equip the person to handle anxiety appropriately by keeping it at optimum level.

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